

Can IFRS Adoption Help Curb Corruption? A Spillover Effect Perspective

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Abstract

Many evidences witnessed that the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) by countries promotes transparency and attracts international capitals. However, whether it may have a positive spillover effect beyond accounting practices in reducing corruption receives scant attention and is worth studying. Using a sample of unbalanced panel of 37 African countries from the WGI- World bank over the period 2002-2016, we found that IFRS adoption from the samples in Africa has a positive impact on corruption. We further found out that the corruption curbing effect of IFRS adoption was stronger in British colonization countries and better law enforcement countries in Africa.

The findings of the study will enlighten the countries which have adopted IFRS to strengthen their law enforcement to maximize the positive effect of IFRS, and will give inspirations and guidance to the countries which are yet to adopt IFRS as a tool of financial protection and management to consider adopting it.

Keywords: Corruption, IFRS Adoption, Rule of law, Economic development, Colonization.

1. Introduction

With many obstacles (terrorism, corruption, poverty & diseases) impeding the developmental trends in Africa, corruption is regarded as the most important challenge amongst them (Sassi & Ali,2017). As stated by prior researches, (e.g. Sassi & Ali,2017; D'Agostino et. al,2016; Dunne & Pieroni,2016; Diaby & Sylwester, 2014), the nature of corruption in African countries is systematic and dissimilar from other regions and sectors due to the limited inflow of foreign direct investment, the expansion of public sector employment, high level of external aid and dependence of commodities and raw materials. Corruption can destroy the legitimacy of a country and as such can bring about the consequence of reducing the effectiveness of public investments and infrastructure. Also, it results in a high shadow economy and derails a country to be less attractive for investors, Štefan Šumah (2018).

Many researches have been done to study how to handle corruption (e.g. Corruption in Africa: what role does ICT play by Sassi & Ali, 2017). However, the studies of linkage on corruption and accounting environment receives scant attention. The essence of International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) is issued by the International Accounting Standard Boards (IASB), with the aim of providing a single, globally – accepted set of financial reporting standards based on clearly articulated principles (IASB, 2015). IFRS standards are expected to improve information quality and capital allocation by contributing to economic efficiency, thus helping investors risk and create opportunities across the world. Furthermore, the adoption of IFRS by a country can lead to an increase in the transparency of financial reporters, low cost of capital and reduction in international reporting cost (Camfferman & Wielhouwer,2019; Gassen,2017; George, Xi Li & Shivakumar,2016). Prior studies found that the adoption of IFRS enhances transparency and disparege information asymmetry (Juniarti, Marcelina & Angela, 2018).

However, whether IFRS adoption may contribute to reducing corruption by bringing incremental disclosure of information and or transparency remains unknown. We argue that, corruption is likely the reason for information obscurity. With adequate transparency, lots of corrupt related transactions can be recorded and

reported, which may cut a firm's motivation to bribe other individuals or institutions, (G. Locatelli, G. Mariani, T. Sainati, M. Greco, 2017; Rose-Ackerman Susan, 2004; World bank, 1997).

Therefore, we utilize a sample of unbalanced panel of 37 African countries from the African development indicators of the world bank for the period 2002-2016 to investigate whether IFRS adoption can explain and help reduce corruption in a country.

Our research has the following contributions. First, it studies corruption as a macro and spillover effect instead of accounting practices. Most of research studied the direct IFRS adoption effect within the firm reporting and capital market. Likewise, many researches highlighted the use of "pre and post" adopting IFRS and forgot to control the simultaneous things. Secondly, it uses developing countries instead of developed countries. Most studies have been done on developed countries, like United States of America, EU countries, where they have developed capital market. While most developing countries, with weak legal system and less developed capital market, receive less attention.

Noteworthy, this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the literature pertaining to the subject and outlines the research hypothesis. Section 3 explains the data and key variables employed in the study. Empirical results are presented in Section 4. Section 5 provides some conclusion.

2. Theoretical Analysis and Hypothesis Development

Despite literature suggesting different definitions for corruption, it is generally defined as an abuse of power and deviance from individual regular duties for an authorized private gain (Aßlander 2017, p. 210; Blackburn, Bose, & Haque (2010, 2006); Shleifer & Vishny, 1993). Also, Fazekas and Kocsis (2017) defined corruption as adhering to suspicious public procurement contracts administered by local mayors to politically affiliated firms. With corruption eroding trust in government institutions and undermining their social contract World Bank (2018), it can be argued to be prevalent and economically costly for both developing and developed countries.

Information asymmetry and obscure can cause corruption. Prior studies, indicated a negative relationship between corruption and information transparency, emphasizing that corruption has an adverse impact on business activity due to lack of transparency and the misallocation of inefficient use of resources, (Mazzia, Slackb & Tsalavoutasc, 2018; Houqe and Monem, 2016; Bryant & Javalgi, 2016; Coutinho de Arruda, & Halter, 2009; Voyer & Beamish, 2004).

Accounting has become an instrument and an object of globalization (Degos et al 2019; Hopper et al. 2017). Increasing internationalization of markets and companies has increased the nature of accounting standardization. With initiatives being implemented to make accounting standards comparable across nations, the World Bank, International Monetary Fund and the International federation of Accounting emphasize the need for its adaptation.

Pertinent to this research, previous accounting literature have examined the relevance and quality of financial information which is said to be apprehended by the level of information asymmetry and indicated the unanimity of accounting standards which ferries with it the potential to increase transparency and improve the quality of financial information for developing countries with active financial and capital market, L.A. Gordon et al., 2012; Shima and Gordon, 2011; Humphrey et al., 2009, Chamisa, 2000.

The IFRS standard demands for a high quality, transparent, and comparable information in financial statements, is expected to help investors in global markets and other users to make economic decisions (Turki et al., 2016). Because of such notion, the augment growth in investment and international trade has brought about the immense adoption of IFRS by both developed and developing countries. Prior research acknowledges the proponents of IFRS as aver, indicating that the standards produce benefits including international comparison, improved transparency (reduction in cost of processing information & asymmetric information), market

efficiency and cross-national investment, and argued that mandatory adoption of IFRS reduces information asymmetry (Juniarti et al. 2018, Turki et al. 2016, Horton et al. (2012) Armstrong et al.,2010).

IFRS is also more scientific which improve information transparent. Taking this line of argumentation, a step further, we advocate that embracing higher-quality accounting standards (such as IFRS) and making greater disclosure is likely to directly reduce corrupt practices on both the demand and supply sides of a country – level corruption (Saha & Ben Ali, 2017; Ben Ali & Sassi, 2016; Habib & Zurawicki, 2002). Other studies have concluded that high-quality accounting practice and assemblages can be both a potentially empowering and a refrainer in a fight against corruption, Changwony&Paterson,2019; Hoskin,2015; Neu, Everett &Rahaman,2013a,2013b,205; Roberts, 2015; Everett et al., 2007). We therefore expect that the impact of accounting on corruption to vary between countries with high-quality accounting practice and those with a weak-quality practice¹. In contrast, the IASB’s current mission of spreading IFRS to the developing countries is expected to help stabilize their economies and foster global trade.

At this point, it is necessary to summarize the situation and rethink that corruption is a major concern for developing countries as it possess serious effect on the welfare and progress of its people , with African countries not an exception(d’Agostino et al.2016).Another research line, argue that the global adoption of IFRS may not be practical or appropriate and also stated that the principles-based standards which provide flexibility, in some cases, excessive flexibility, to companies that may engage in earnings management, leads to a reduction in accounting quality(Bryce et al. 2015, Barth et al., 2008; Jeanjean and Stolowy, 2008). A number of African countries have adopted or plan to adopt IFRS. (Groß et al., 2015), this on the other hand, indicates that African countries who adopt IFRS may have their own “consumption needs”. Nevertheless, it can be argued that more emerging and developing countries in Africa tends to compete in the global market and are more willing to adopt IFRS and have a uniform accounting standard. IFRS reduces an important barrier by alleviating an information asymmetry between a home country and a foreign user of financial information, Young & Guenther (2003), Hung and Subramanyam (2007), Barth et al. (2008), Chen et al. (2010), Chalmers et al. (2011) and Chua et al. (2012) concluded that the adoption of IFRS improves accounting quality.

If adopting IFRS is expected to lower information asymmetry cost, then it is expected to be beneficial to African countries because of their significant reliance on inflows of foreign capital for economic and industrial development. Existing studies, also agree with the empirical evidence by arguing that the increase of information disclosure can lower information asymmetry by making it available to investors (e.g., Horton et al 2013; Zhou, 2007; Leuz & Verrecchia, 2000).

To address why IFRS adoption can be an important drive in curbing corruption in Africa, we discuss how a complementary relationship between high-quality accounting practices, strong legal enforcement and colonization of a country might better explain variations in corruption across African countries. Complementarity is discernible in both the theoretical underpinnings and the empirical analyses of the accounting and corruption literature. The antidote to corruption has been widely recommended by IFRS due to the reason that lack of accountability and transparency heartens corruption and that the culture of secrecy encourages corruption (Shleifer & Vishny, 1993). It is assumed that accounting is likely to reduce corruption and also International Financial Reporting Standards helps in the mitigation of corruption and helps countries with low quality or non-existence of accounting standards to improve their accounting environment by adopting

¹ Brusca and Condor (2002) identify eight possible reasons why the harmonization of national accounting systems with international accounting systems might be difficult to achieve: political and administrative environment, interests and the formation of professionals, public accounting regulatory mechanisms, sources of financial resource, key users of financial reports, the objectives of public financial reporting, the organization of the public sector and the legal system.

it (Hope et al., 2006).

Advocates of IFRS claim that Financial transparency can lead to an effort of increasing or improve financial reporting quality and reduce information acquisition costs, thereby may attract and increase investors' willingness to invest across borders (e.g., SEC, 2008; Tweedie, 2008).

Mandatory adoption of IFRS improves the accounting environment through an approach where products and services produced from developed countries are perceived to be of high quality due the high quality of accounting standards pursued by the developed countries (Agbonifoh & Elimian, 1999). Findings from prior studies in regard to the impact of IFRS adoption on accounting quality concluded in their research that the adoption of IFRS improves accounting quality. (M. Bryce et al. 2015; Chua et al. 2012; Chalmers et al. 2011 and Chen et al. 2010) and also, the mandatory and voluntarily adoption of IFRS at the state level is a significant commitment which requires constant monitoring and enforcing the practice of new accounting standards but not only educating preparers and auditors (Preiato et al., 2015). According to related research, the result of weak-quality accounting practice can provide opportunities for incumbent politicians to withhold or manipulate monitoring information which can inevitably lead to conceal their rent-seeking behavior and can weaken the role of decentralization monitoring mechanisms, but a good accounting standard can help in reducing corruption. (World Bank, 2017; Cruz, Keefer, & Labonne, 2016; Kramon, 2016; Singer, 2009).

A recent witness of the widespread difference of IFRS among countries, including more about IFRS than GAAP. IFRS is more flexible and its increasingly so than the GAAP, which focus on stringent rules-bases regulations and its of more rigid nature. The US expression of its support for International Accounting Standards (IAS) indicates its greater value and significant benefit even though the US has still not yet adopted such standards. Nevertheless, even if the quality of standards under IFRS is greater than GAAP the US would still be unwilling to implement IFRS because of its significant cost & obstacles towards. With the considerable rising in the number of emerging countries having adopted or introducing to converging to IFRS, we can properly say the IFRS is better than GAAP. Nonetheless, note that we are not arguing that GAAP is necessarily inferior to IFRS, but rather that IFRS may better fit the African countries' current stage of economic and institutional development than GAAP. (e.g. S.A. Zeff, 2007; Lam et al. 2014)

Low transparency is one of the factors of curbing corruption in an African country. Now most accounting transactions are being recognized in the financial report, indicating that a great deal of transactions related to corruption may be presented in the financial reports. Secondly, the implementation of more transparency will help improve stakeholder's surveillance. With Owolabi & Iyoha, (2012) also indicating in their findings that IFRS adoption will be potentially beneficial to a wide range of stakeholders.

In a nutshell, the study suggests that an improvement of accounting environment in country level mitigate corruption by ensuring disclosure, transparency and instituting accountability practice. The adoption of IFRS can be of immense help to African countries which can significantly improve their accounting system and environment. Likewise, detour to the implementing and enforcing a set of new accounting standards, the benefits of IFRS adoption in reducing corruption are likely to increase over time. Formally, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 1: Ceteris paribus, after the adoption of IFRS, corruption reduced.

In developing countries, among them many African countries accounting standards are often a legacy of colonial rule, (Degos et al. 2019). With a significant direct influence from the colonization of the continent by the Western, Falola (2004). Hence, explaining the colonization experience in Africa, which has had a significant impact on growth, by producing ethnic distortions and political instabilities. This argument is also informed by the evidence in the accounting literature, which showed in-depth evidence that the impact of IFRS adoption on

country-level corruption can be affected by the influence of colonization. In 2005, EU countries adopted IFRS mandatory mainly due to the recognition of high – quality and transparent financial report, Gulhan Suadiye (2017). Because IASB is located in the UK, there is the tendency for English-speaking African countries to easily adopt IFRS as compared to the French-speaking African countries, where the convergence to adopt IFRS is low. This can be attributed to language, education and a common system based on their colonial allegiance. Furthermore, the convergence of accounting standards in the African countries formerly colonized by France involves a succession of groupings, resistances and abandonments, linked to multiple factors attributable to their status as former colonies. This indicates accounting standards reflect an “inheritance” rather than any closer connection (Degos et al.2019).

It is expected that the adoption of IFRS will rather not end the history of accounting standards in Africa, but rather begin a new phase of the ongoing development. Based on this, we predict that for French Colonies, the adoption of IFRS is like an external shot. This resultantly changes their environment, hence a reduction in corruption.

Hypothesis 2: Ceteris paribus, the colonization of African countries has a direct effect on the impact of adoption of IFRS on Corruption.

H2a: British Colonies’ adoption of IFRS has a positive impact on corruption

H2b: French Colonies’ non - adoption of IFRS has a negative impact on corruption

The legal system, thus the rule of law and accounting standard in Africa is significantly influenced by its colonial rulers, where African countries colonized by the British follow the English common law, with countries colonized by the French followed by the French civil law (Lee & Schltz,2012). These countries turn to follow the accounting standards of the countries that colonized them. Ali & Hwang 1999 established that countries with strict legal enforcement tend to have higher quality accounting. M. DeFond et al.,2018 stated that foreign investors from countries with weak legal and economic institutions, similar to those in China, reduce their investment by a greater amount than foreign investors from countries with strong institutions. Furthermore, Prior research finds that IFRS has positive capital market consequence, particularly in countries with strong legal and economic institutions (Covrig et al., 2007; DeFond et al., 2011). A common finding in the above studies is that the benefits of IFRS adoption accrue primarily to firms where IFRS is likely to be credibly implemented, such as those in countries where legal enforcement is strong. Also, the easy convergence to adopt IFRS by English-speaking African countries is said to be because they stemmed from Anglo-Saxon law which depends more of interpretation and works with high-level professionals as compared to the French-speaking countries who are attached to the French accounting standards stemming from a tradition of written law.

Hypothesis 3: Ceteris paribus, a stronger legal enforcement of an African country has a direct effect on Corruption.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data

A sample of 37 African countries over the years 2002-2016 is selected from World bank. This period marks the immediate Pre-adoption and Post – adoption reporting periods. These countries represent emerging countries with similar backgrounds prior to the adoption and non-adoption of the IFRS as a standard

3.2 Variables

We build on Rammana and Sletten (2014) database by using and updating the main source of information on each country’s time and extent of adoption. Similar to Houque and Monem (2013,2016), we used a

perception-based corruption index instead of actual corruption as a measure of corruption. Prior corruption literature provides empirical evidence that perception-based corruption measures are more valid measures of corruption compared to actual corruption measures. According to Triesman (2007) perception-based corruption measures are highly correlated with real factors that usually lead to corruption.

Control of Corruption (corrup) index developed by Kaufmann et al. (2012) as part of the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) project is our measure of country-level corruption and dependent variable for this study². The WGI measures are reported in two ways: in the percentile rank terms, ranging from 0 (lowest) to 100 (highest) and in the standard normal units of the governance indicator, ranging from -2.5 to 2.5 among all countries (Kaufmann et al., 2011). To assist the interpretation of our findings, our index is expressed in standard normal unit and we mark the index corrup with higher scores indicating less corruption in an African country.

We measure IFRS adoption (Adp) as the number of years since an African country mandatorily adopted the IFRS. We obtain IFRS adoption dates from the "IFRS Adoption by a country" survey conducted by PricewaterhouseCoopers (PWC) in October, 2015. We compute Adp by indicating the pre-adoption period and post adoption period.

We also consider some control variables such as rule of law (rlaw), which is one of the six dimensions of the Worldwide Governance Indicators constructed by the World Bank based on a large number of responses on surveys from enterprises, citizens and experts in these countries. It also, assess to which extent citizens abide by the rules of their country. This includes the enforcement of the contracts, the property rights, and the courts. The higher scores, indicating strong rule of law and vice versa)

The level of economic development is evaluated by two operationalized dimensions; thus, Gross domestic product (gdpmkt) and Inflation (Iflcpi) which stands for the annual inflation rate measured by the increase in the consumer price index over a one-year period.

The world bank's measure of the extent of disclosure ranges from 0 to 10, with a higher score indicating greater disclosure. Our measure of the extent of disclosure (discedl) indicates how well minority shareholders are protected through disclosure against self-dealing in related-party transactions. In addition, we will categorize our sampling of 37 African countries into their Colonial heritage (Col).

We further examine whether IFRS adoption mitigate corruption after controlling the country-level variables as well as the adoption year and also regress the indicating variables. The study employed the models of Houqe & Monem (2016a) and Triesman (2007) to apply it on African data thus developing countries to ascertain the impact of IFRS adoption on corruption.

Table 1. Description of variables and data source

VARIABLES	MEASURE	DESCRIPTION OF VARIABLE	SOURCE
DEPENDENT VARIABLE			
Control of Corruption	Corrup	Reflects perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as "capture" of the state by elites and private interests.	Kaufmann et al. (2012); The Worldwide Governance Indicators, 2018 Update
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES			

² For a detailed discussion of the methodology, see Kaufmann et al. (2011)

Adoption Year	ADP	The years since a country adopted mandatory IFRS	IFRS Adoption by Country” survey conducted by IFRS Adoption by Country” survey conducted by PricewaterhouseCoopers in September -October 2015
Rule of Law	Rlaw	Reflects perceptions of the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society, and in particular the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, the police, and the courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence.	Governance Indicators, 2018 Update
GDP growth (annual %)	GDP.mktp	Annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices based on constant local currency. Aggregates are based on constant 2010 U.S. dollars.	World development indicators/ world bank
Inflation, (annual %)	IFL.cpi	Inflation as measured by the annual growth rate of the GDP implicit deflator shows the rate of price change in the economy as a whole. The GDP implicit deflator is the ratio of GDP in current local currency to GDP in constant local currency.	World development indicators/ world bank
Extent of director liability index (0-10)	Discedl	Extent of director liability index is used as the proxy for investor protection.	Doing Business Report, TheWorld Bank (2002-2016)
Colonial preference	Col	Countries in Africa being colonized by the Western -world	Doing Business Report, TheWorld Bank (2002-2016)

3.3 Model

The objective in this study is not to ascertain the corruption determinants in African countries but rather focus on assessing the impact of IFRS adoption on corruption after regressing the condign indicating variables. This study considers constructing a model for corruption using measures of IFRS, and use legal system and a proxy for economic development and colonial heritage as control variables. find that two measures are significant in explaining corruption when controlling for economic development. The model is referenced to Treisman (2000); Houqe & Monem (2016). We replicate the series of nested regressions found in Treisman (2000), which has the influence of the legal system, colonial tradition, economic development, to ensure that accounting environment is significant when controlling for economic and other variables, (Malagueño et al., 2010). We therefore display our results in a manner similar to Treisman’s, where a single model, results is displayed, with estimate additional models, displaying each model with another column in the table. We consider a linear regression model as shown in the equation below:

$$\text{Corrup}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{Adp}_{it} + \varphi_2 \text{Rlaw}_{it} + \gamma_3 (\text{GDPmkt})_{it} + \psi_4 (\text{Iflcpi})_{it} + \mu_5 (\text{discedl})_{it} + \lambda_6 (\text{Col})_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where *i* and *t* characterized each country and time period.

3.4 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2, presents sample descriptive statistics. The mean and median are closely related, whilst the standard deviation is homogenous in nature. The mean and median of Control of Corruption and Adoption of IFRS are -0.42(-0.52) and 0.72(1.00) respectively. This indicates that the average African country is highly corrupt with

such mean (median) score, thus a minimum of -1.45 being perceived as the most corrupt African country, to a maximum of 1.22 as the least corrupt African country. Furthermore, the standard deviation of 0.62, shows the large gap between African countries, with some having high corruption rate and others low corruption rate. In terms of rule of law, the mean (median) score is -0.44(-0.47) with the minimum of -1.85 and the maximum of 1.08. The mean values of the gross domestic product and Inflation being the determinants of economic development are 4.96 and 6.18 respectively.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of key variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Median
Corrup	317	-0.42	0.62	-1.45	1.22	-0.52
Adp	317	0.72	0.45	0	1	1
Rlaw	317	-0.44	0.62	-1.85	1.08	-0.47
Gdp.mktp	317	4.96	4.46	-20.6	26.4	4.7
Ifl.cpi	317	6.18	6.32	-2.41	44.4	5.03
Discedl	317	4.87	2.11	0	8	5
Col	317	1.1	0.93	0	3	1

Note: All variable definitions appear in Table 1.

** Variables winsorised at 1% and 99%

Table 3, presents the Pearson correlation matrix. The correlation between adoption of IFRS (adp), rule of law and the extent of disclosure show positive signs. Control of corruption has a strong positive correlation with rule of law and the extent of disclosure and are statistically significant (two tailed p-value < 0.01). The positive correlation between the corrup and rlaw variables signifies that potential investors are better protected in the least corrupt African country and can be estimated that investor protection has an impact on corruption. The absence of correlation between the adoption of IFRS and control of corruption aggrandize the assumptions that the control of corruption doesn't have any impact on the control variables.

The significant correlation between Col, discedl and the economic determinants, shows a better accounting environment and an increased economic growth can cause an effect on the colonization of an African country. From all indications, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is multicollinearity in the variables.

Table 3. Pearson's correlation coefficients

	Corrup	Adp	Rlaw	Gdp.mktp	Ifl.cpi	Discedl	Col
Corrup	1						
Adp	.062	1					
Rlaw	.886**	.092	1				
Gdp.mktp	-.013	-.053	-.054	1			

lfl.cpi	.018	-.102	.050	.208**	1		
Discedl	.220**	.110	.242**	-.169**	-.093	1	
Col	.046	-.052	-.010	.235**	.203**	-.209**	1

Note: All variable definitions appear in Table 1.

*, ** and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

Variables winsorised at 1% and 99%

4. Empirical Result

4.1 General Regression

Table 4 reports the estimation results for the model using the OLS regression technique with a correction for the heteroscedasticity of the standard error. Adoption of IFRS shows a positive coefficient of 0.071 and is statistically significant ($t = 2.32$) as expected at the 0.01 significance level. This sequel confirms that the higher the corruption level of an African country is, the higher the tendency to adopt IFRS and enhances our estimation that an African country's adoption of IFRS lays positive effect on lowering corruption. Thus, H1 is supported.

Furthermore, using the adoption of IFRS as a dependent variable in column 2, we find negative coefficients for both discedl and col variables, but statistically significant. This can be estimated that a country with high corruption level, would prefer to adopt IFRS to have a high-quality accounting standard and improve its information transparency to aid in reducing the corruption level of a country. Equally for the control of corruption, its significantly and positivity influences the IFRS adoption by an African country. This indicates that an accounting environment, colonial heritage and the control of corruption factor has an influence in the adoption of IFRS.

The estimated coefficient on the control variables generally have the expected positive signs although there are some which are not robust to our choice of estimation technique³. We expect a negative coefficient on the variable inflation in all the regressions. Our estimation outcomes also elaborate that the effects of inflation on corruption is significant for the overall sample. An increase in corruption can be caused by a high level of inflation rate.

Countries' colonial heritage is very significant in predicting the current level of corruption. Based on the results in column 1, it can be estimated that former British colonies in Africa have significant lower corruption. With the French colonies not differed clearly in corruption level. This regression, however seems to indicate something specific about the British colonies in Africa. The existence of a positive coefficient between corrup and discedl, indicates a better accounting environment for African countries, but further support the idea that, there is a significant upturn in the accounting environment of the British colonized countries in Africa who have adopted IFRS, which in turns to reduce corruption in British Colonized African countries; than African countries colonized by the French.

The positive coefficient and statistically significant of the GDP per market, enhances the emphasizes that a high income tends to curb corruption in most African countries. This outcome remains robust across subsamples with different developmental level, suggesting that the impact of increase economic growth is comparable for both British and French colonized countries in Africa. For African countries with low levels of economic development, one would expect significant effects of corruption, since corruption impede development and as an economic malady, becomes a reason behind weak economic performance. In conformity with previous studies Zeghal and Mhedhbi (2006), IFRS adoption is more permissible by the developing countries with high

³ All statistical test in this study except those in table 3 are one-tailed test

economic growth.

The results presented in column 5, affirm the indication that a stronger legal enforcement can help reduce corruption in Africa, with the adoption of IFRS, rule of law and colonial heritage achieving statistical significance. This propels the tendency for a country with the common legal system to increase its adoption of IFRS.

Table 4. Results of OLS regressions on corruption in 37 countries (dependent variable is corruption, 2002-2016).

$$\text{Corrup}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{Adp}_{it} + \varphi_2 \text{Rlaw}_{it} + \gamma_3 (\text{GDPmkt})_{it} + \psi_4 (\text{Iflcpi})_{it} + \mu_5 (\text{discedl})_{it} + \lambda_6 (\text{Col})_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{----- (1)}$$

Variables	Adp	Rlaw	Gdpmktp	Iflcpi	Discedl	Col
Co-eff	0.072	0.399	0.003	-0.006	0.049	0.323
t-statistic	2.35***	5.13***	1.91***	-2.97***	3.70***	9.20***
Intercept	-1.514	(-8.08)***		F-statistic (p-value)		535.08
Adj.R ²	0.957			No. of Obs.		317

Note: All variable definitions appear in Table 1.

*, ** and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% respectively. t-statistics in brackets
Variables winsorised by year at 1% and 99%. Standard errors clustered by country

4.1 Further Analysis

We examine any potential interaction between (col*adp) and also (rlaw*adp) in reducing corruption in Africa, thus we use at least two period lagged variable of interaction term as valid instrument.

$$\text{Corrup}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Adp}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{Rlaw}_{it} + \alpha_3 (\text{Col} * \text{adp})_{it} + \alpha_4 (\text{GDPmkt})_{it} + \alpha_5 (\text{Iflcpi})_{it} + \alpha_6 (\text{discedl})_{it} + \alpha_7 (\text{Col})_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{---(2)}$$

$$\text{Corrup}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Adp}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{Rlaw}_{it} + \alpha_3 (\text{rlaw} * \text{adp})_{it} + \alpha_4 (\text{GDPmkt})_{it} + \alpha_5 (\text{Iflcpi})_{it} + \alpha_6 (\text{discedl})_{it} + \alpha_7 (\text{Col})_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{----- (3)}$$

4.2.1 Colonization

We further investigate whether pre and post adoption of IFRS has any significant effect on African countries. This interaction variable is to test whether the adoption of IFRS makes any difference to corruption between British colonies in Africa (coded 1) and French colonies in Africa (coded 0). The control of corruption variable and its adoption interaction are both significant at least 0.01 level in all of the estimated equations, the estimated results clearly indicate that based on colonial heritage the adoption of IFRS has a positive effect on corruption. This estimation supports previous results and shows a positive and significant coefficient of the interaction terms.

Most notably, from table 5 we find that the, colonization, strength of legal enforcement (rlaw) and better accounting environment (discedl) are significant under the pre and post adoption period.

Table 5. Results of OLS regressions testing the effect of IFRS adoption and colonization on corruption in 37

countries (dependent variable is corruption, 2002-2016)

$$\text{Corrup}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Adp}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{Rlaw}_{it} + \alpha_3 (\text{Col} * \text{adp})_{it} + \alpha_4 (\text{GDPmkt})_{it} + \alpha_5 (\text{Ifcpi})_{it} + \alpha_6 (\text{discedl})_{it} + \alpha_7 (\text{Col})_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Variables	Adp	Rlaw	Gdpmktp	Ifcpi	Discedl	Col	Col*adp
Co-eff	0.628	0.397	0.003	-0.005	0.005	0.321	0.897
t-statistic	1.49**	5.05***	1.98***	-2.95***	3.73***	8.59***	1.70**
Intercept	-1.514	(-8.56)***		F-statistic (p-value)		522.98	
Adj.R ²	0.955			No. of Obs.		317	

Note: All variable definitions appear in Table 1.

*, ** and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% respectively. t-statistics in brackets.

Variables winsorised by year at 1% and 99%. Standard errors clustered by country.

4.2.1 Law

Table 6, indicates the interaction variable rlaw * adp. We find that colonial heritage, rule of law and economic development variables are statistically significant, suggesting that these variables have an impact on the adoption of IFRS, especially the rule of law, which indicates that a stronger legal enforcement system can help reduce corruption in an African country. These results indicate, that the improvement in corruption that African countries expects from the adoption of IFRS depends on the impact of colonization, strength of the legal system and its accounting environment in a country. Also, all these results suggest that African countries who adopted IFRS benefit more in terms of lower corruption with a strong legal system compared to non-adopters.

A cogent explanation is that adopters of IFRS tends to have high quality accounting standards, hence a better accounting environment and a good economic growth and also a stronger legal system. In addition, for non-adopter' countries, it can be estimated there would be significant effects of corruption on their economic growth, attributable to increased uncertainty and instability.

Table 6. Results of OLS regressions testing the effect of IFRS adoption and colonization on corruption in 37 countries (dependent variable is corruption, 2002-2016)

$$\text{Corrup}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Adp}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{Rlaw}_{it} + \alpha_3 (\text{rlaw} * \text{adp})_{it} + \alpha_4 (\text{GDPmkt})_{it} + \alpha_5 (\text{Ifcpi})_{it} + \alpha_6 (\text{discedl})_{it} + \alpha_7 (\text{Col})_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

Variables	Adp	Rlaw	Gdpmktp	Ifcpi	Discedl	Col	rlaw*adp
Co-eff	0.0147	0.786	0.005	-0.005	0.005	0.33	0.155
t-statistic	0.19	12.82**	1.66**	-1.76**	0.67	2.62**	2.15**
Intercept	-0.919	-0.86		F-statistic (p-value)		223.48	
Adj.R ²	0.93			No. of Obs.		317	

Note: All variable definitions appear in Table 1.

, ** and * denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% respectively. t-statistics in brackets. Variables winsorised by year at 1% and 99%. Standard errors clustered by country.*

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examined the impact of IFRS adoption and the extent of disclosure on corruption in Africa for the period of 2002 to 2016 for an unbalanced panel of 37 countries. The study was motivated by the research gap in the area of IFRS adoption despite the accounting field's fundamental focus on efficiency, control and disclosure.

The study found that IFRS adoption and colonization in the samples of Africa has positive impact on corruption, and disclosure of directors' liability to protect investors' interest has positive impact on corruption by controlling them with economic growth and the strength of the legal system. We also find that African countries who adopted IFRS benefit more from a better accounting environment compared to the non-adopters. From the study it can be indicated that the adoption of IFRS can help French – colonized countries to improve their informational and accounting environment. Also, it can be said that, the indefatigable effort of promoting IFRS at the political level by IASB has paid off in matters ranging from endorsement to mandatory adoption. We find that an economy's development can be sustained by curbing corruption in Africa. Secondly, a robust legal system for detecting, investigating, and prosecuting acts of corruption are critical to the effectiveness of curbing corruption in developing countries.

Finally, a typical case in Ghana for example and other African countries relates to the fact that, though most countries have adopted IFRS as a drive or landscape tool of correction to corruption, however, Ghana for instance is slow to implement the ROSC (AA) recommendations for IFRS adoption due to lack of institutional and professional capacity. With regards to the unintended consequences, IFRS adoption has therefore made international professional qualifications such as Association of Certified Chartered Accountants popular in Africa; hence, national accounting qualifications are not attractive to prospective accountants. Similarly, IFRS adoption has created a competitive advantage for some audit firms because companies in IFRS countries prefer the services of these firms to that of the local audit firms.

Therefore, a key recommendation that requires consideration relates to the fact that, international organizations that suggests IFRS to Africa, such as the IFRS foundation, International Monetary Fund and World Bank, should take concrete and decisive steps to build the sustainable professional and institutional capacity of these countries before persuading them to adopt IFRS, because in Africa, there is a normative observation which relates to the fact that adopting a law is easy but operationalizing the policy implementation seem a major challenge.

Finally, it will be prudent if non-adopters of IFRS may consider the adoption of IFRS. Likewise, for those who have adopted IFRS, the consideration for its enforcement to enhance IFRS education is recommended. The findings of the study are best regarded as suggestive rather than definitive hence more research is recommended into the area of IFRS adoption in the developing countries.

Appendix A. List of African countries included in the sample

Adopted Countries		Non - Adopted Countries	
Algeria	Mauritius	Benin	Guinea-Bissau
Angola	Morocco	Central African Republic	Mali
Botswana	Namibia	Chad	Niger
Burkina Faso	Nigeria	Cote d'Ivoire	Senegal
Burundi	Rwanda	Democratic rep. of Congo	Togo

Cameroon	Seychelles	Equatorial Guinea	Tunisia
Egypt, Arab Rep.	Sierra Leone	Guinea	
Ethiopia	South Africa		
Gabon	Swaziland		
Gambia	Tanzania		
Ghana	Zambia		
Liberia	Zimbabwe		

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